

Publication Form SFB 1552**SFB-ID:**

This form contains all important data related to a publication within the SFB1552. Furthermore, it serves as proof both within the SFB 1552 and to the DFG as the funding organisation that the publication process has been in line with the guidelines of the research data management policy. This includes the publication of the research data and metadata associated with the publication in order to ensure verifiability, reproducibility and transparency of results along with long-term availability and reusability of data. The SFB-ID will be filled out by the SFB-Team.

Information on research publication:

Title	
Article Type	Research article, communication, review, ...
Journal	
Volume	
Issue	
Pages	
Persistent identifier	DOI, ISBN, ...
Date of publication	YYMMDD (online or printed)
First Author	Name, Institution, contact details, ORCID
Correspondent Author	Name, Institution, contact details, ORCID
Project Number	A0X, B0Y, C0Z, Z01, ...
Further Author	Names
Supporting information	Identifier, Description

Information on data publication:

Infrastructure	Zenodo, Gutenberg Open Science, Chemotion Repository
Date of publication	YYYYMMDD
Persistent identifier	DOI, ISBN, ...